

Music in the Convent Life of the St Adalbert's Abbey in Staniątki (PL-STAb)*

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1 Role of music in the convent life

Over the centuries, the rich musical culture of the convent in Staniątki took a variety of forms. The foundation of the musical life was always the sung Officium. As Sister Kolumba Łozińska writes:

“[...] we have proven that in a Benedictine convent the maintenance of a choir, which implied the solemn singing of the breviary was the first duty of the convent. In compliance with the celebrations of the church year and in accordance with the content arrangement of the Benedictine breviary used by the nuns of Staniątki, all feasts of the Holy Virgin Mary are at times celebrated very solemnly”.

At least from the second half of the 16th century (and probably earlier than that) the singing of the Officium was accompanied by an organ. The post-visitation instructions issued by bishop Duke Jerzy Radziwiłł in 1597 prove that there were two instruments in the convent at the time. One of them was situated in the church and the other was situated in the convent choir.

“Under the newly built Choir, make a modest lining, in the chapel, raise the walls higher above the organ — like it is done under the drawn curtain [...] Take down the entrance from the side of the organ and build it from the side of the sacristy; cover the organ itself in such a way that it cannot be seen at all for the convent choir”¹.

Particularly interesting are Radziwiłł's instructions in regard to the singing. The practices of performing Polish hymns during the mass did not escape the bishop's attention. Those were probably hymns contained in the hymnbooks of Staniątki.

“The prioress should try to ensure that the nuns have their own breviaries, psalters and other convent books, printed in Venice or elsewhere, according to which they

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¹ PL-STAb, *Reforma życia zakonnego przez Wizyty duchowne, Wizyta Isza JW: księcia Radziwiła roku 1597*. (The Reform of Convent Life By Clerical Visits. The Visit of His Excellency Duke Radziwiłł in 1597) pp. 1–2.

would perform the Choral — without adding or deducting anything; — just like what we have now encountered in *Sufragije* and in *Benedicamus*. However, the *Officia* of the Patrons the nuns need to celebrate according to the old custom — in compliance with the convent *Breviary*. Also during the Holy Mass, the sisters need to observe the *Missal* in all; without adding or deducting anything, as heretofore. In *Kyrye*, in *Gloria*, in *Credo* they shall not sing Polish hymns. Whereas, at other times, after having celebrated the Mass and other *Officia* — they may sing hymns in separate, if they wish”.

The examples of troped parts of the Mass we can find in the hymnbooks of Staniątki, i.a. in the oldest of them (St A). The leaves 49v–50v contain the musical setting of *Sanctus* with tropes.

Figure 1: “Troped Sanctus” (St E, leaves 49v–50r)

We can find at least a few examples of Polish tropes in the Mass settings in the examined Staniątki repertoire. During my research, I managed to discover an interesting source containing a written record of the criticism expressed during the visitation of the custom of adding the Polish text to parts of the Mass. In the Stefanyk Library in Lvov, a manuscript has been preserved (call number: M Ben 75), in which we can find *Rotuły ktore spiewac sie maią wiutrznią Bozego narodenia na mszej swietej nocnej* (*Rotuły* to be sung on Christmas Eve during the midnight Holy Mass (leaves 41r–48v). It is an extremely valuable find which sheds a new light on the performance of the popular, 17th and 18th century *Rotuły*, as Christmas carolls were called in the 17th and 18th century. In an article on Polish religious hymns in the manuscripts of the Benedictines of Przemyśl, Rev. Tadeusz Bratkowski characterizes the practice of performing the *Rotuły* [Bratkowski, 2001, 81–84]. The author mentions the hymn *Quem pastores* included in the hymnbook St A, which contains also Polish text. In the manuscript we can read that it is a hymn to be performed at *Czasu Narodzenia Bozego na pierwszej mszej* (The Time of Christmas during the first Mass). Alas, the manuscript from Staniątki contains only the text of the lyrics, which is divided between four ‘choirs’. This notation method suggests that the text was sung to one of the popular melodies. Bratkowski, while writing about the possible way of performing

the *Rotuły*, proposes a thesis that “[...] it could be like this: the cantor sang the Latin text of the stanza, the nuns sang the Latin chorus, and all those gathered in the church joined in to sing the Polish text” [Bratkowski, 2001, 85]. However, a question that arises is whether the singing was performed as an independent composition or whether it was treated as tropes to liturgical texts. The Lvov manuscript indicates an extremely elaborate and dramatised performance with a division into choirs, and also with the organ accompaniment. Already the very initial fragment of the composition proves how this upset the message of the liturgical text itself.

Obviously, we do not have any certainty that the Benedictines of Staniątki interfered with the texts of the *ordinarium* to the same extent as their Lvov counterparts.² It is beyond any doubt, however, that these interferences were big enough to attract the attention of Bishop Radziwiłł. Nonetheless, what remains symptomatic is the fact that the custom of adding Polish hymns to liturgical singing must have been firmly rooted. In as much as the particularly solemn form of celebrating the liturgy during Christmas does not come as a surprise, the post-visitation instructions unequivocally demonstrate that the convent pursued this practice also outside the festive seasons.

However, the recommendations of the church authorities in regard to singing were probably enforced quite conscientiously. During the next visitation in 1599 the bishop — albeit clearly not fully satisfied with the implementation of his instructions³ — did not raise many objections. Essential information, however, can be found in the fragment of a text discussing the singing of the psalms in a choir:

“In the choir the benches should be thick at the forms, for the younger. For the first psalm the right choir will be sitting, and for the second psalm the left choir will be sitting. When the organist is playing, the psalms that he is playing shall be read by two nuns in the choir. [...] Laughs, errors in singing, slow arrival in the choir [...] shall be severely punished”.

Magdalena Walter-Mazur draws attention to the fact that against the recommendations of the Rules⁴ in the 17th century nuns of the congregation of Chełmno did play the organ, and in the 18th century they played also other instruments. The permanent presence of the organist in the Staniątki convent and the fact that he accompanied the singing of the *Officium* demonstrates the more diligent observation of the bans in this matter, at least at the time of Radziwiłł visitations.

What remains an extremely interesting issue is the matter of the possible engagement of nuns in the performance of vocal-instrumental music by an ensemble. The practising of such solutions in Polish Benedictine convents has been confirmed by the research done by Magdalena Walter-Mazur. In Sandomierz, for instance, in the 18th century there was a group of nuns who were

² Let us also take into account a certain time distance between the analysed sources — the Staniątki manuscript is dated for 1587, whereas the Lvov record of the *Rotuły* comes most probably from the beginnings of the 18th century, although in the catalogue it is dated (probably erroneously) as a 17th century source.

³ *Despite the fact that A. D. 1597, during our first Visit, we adequately showed You what you should do and what you should avoid [...] nonetheless, in some matters you needed an explanation [...] therefore, this year, we assigned some articles to you for you to observe them.* PL-STAb, *Reforma...*, *Wizyta 2ga [...] roku 1599*, (The Reform..., The 2nd Visit [...] in 1599), p. 14.

⁴ E.g. the Toruń and Chełmno Rules forbade nuns to play any instruments. Cf. [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 265].

Figure 2: "Rotuły" – a hymnbook of the Benedictines of Lvov, M Ben 75, leaves 49v–50r

Rotuły
które spiewac się mają
wewnętrznią Bożego narodzenia
na mszy świętej nocnej

Rękopis benedyktynek lwowskich
XVIII w. [?]

Et in ter - ra pax ho - mi - ni - bus bo - - ne vo - lun -
ta - tis lau - da - mus te Be - ne - di - - - ci - mus
te A - do - ra - - mus te glo - ri - - - fi - ca - - - mus te.

po organach
1. Chór Quem pa - sto - res lau - da - ue - re 2. Chór Qui - bus An - ge - li di - ce - re
3. Chór Ab - sit no - bis iam ti - me - re 4. Chór Na - tus est rex glo - ri - ae
Pu - e - ri na - ti - ui - tas so - le - mnis est fe - - sti - ui - tas glo - ri - o - sae De - i - tas
e - mi - cu - it Plau - di - te pu - e - ru - li vo - ce co - ra - li Li li li pu - er Li li li pu - er vo - ce co - ra - li
1. Chór Bra - cia sio - stri po - slu - chai - cie 2. Chór O Ie - su - sie sie ba - dai - cie
3. Chór Kto - re - go iest po - ro - dzi - la 4. Chór Ma - ri - a bez bo - le - sci
Chri - stus sie nam na - ro - - dzil iak z da - wna pro - ro - ko - wan był kro - le - stwo
nam nie - bie - skie o - two - rzil. We - sel - cie sie dzie - tki z ma - le - go dzie - cią - tka
Li li li dzi - cie li li li na - do - bne dzis na - ro - dzo - ne.
na chorze
Gra - - ti - as a - - gi - mus ti - bi Pro - pter ma - gnam
glo - ri - am tu - am Do - mi - ne De - us rex coe - le - - stis
De - us Pa - ter o - - mni - - po - tens. Do - mi - ne
fi - li v - ni - ge - - ni - te Ie - su chri - ste.

accepted to the convent without a dowry but on account of their musical talents. What is more, the rhythm of their day diverged slightly from the rhythm of the day of other nuns — they were sometimes released of canonical hours to be able to prepare themselves for the performance.⁵ We, unfortunately, do not dispose of data that would authorise similar conclusions with regard to the customs of the Staniątki nuns. However, if we combine certain facts, we may assume that, like in Sandomierz, nuns could actively participate in performing vocal-instrumental music.

One of the most significant premises can be found in the hymnbooks. In the hymnbook St E written down by Boczkowski we can find the piece *Huc omnes qui pugnatis* in honour of the Holy Virgin Mary. The piece is for two high parts (clefs C1) and basso continuo.

The most interesting parts in the score are places where vocal parts are silent — on the basis of notes in the part of the organ we may confirm that these short sections (measures 3, 5, 11) were enhanced by a violin. It is very possible that its part was not written down because it could have been improvised. Another proof of the practice of including instruments in the performance of the hymns is also a note that Boczkowski placed on a staff in his own composition *Ave sponsa creatoris*.⁶

The note reading *Symphonia Si placet Simili modo* means that between the subsequent verses of the piece, and, at their own discretion, the performers may add an instrumental interlude. This brief ritornell was certainly either improvised or based on the motivics of vocal parts. *Symphonia* could also be a simple instrumental repetition of the vocal material. Irrespective of the actual solutions, this means that Staniątki followed the practice of the vocal-instrumental performance of the hymn repertoire. *Ave sponsa creatoris* is a composition authored by Boczkowski who marked it clearly by writing: “Auth Casim. Boczkowski O[rganarius] S[taniąteciensis]”. There are no data permitting to solve the question of attribution of the hymn *Huc omnes qui pugnatis*; in stylistic terms, however, it represents a later repertoire. It is thus legitimate to ask whether adding instrumental parts or the instrumental performance of vocal parts (in the form of e.g. a ritornell) was a practice introduced by Boczkowski or whether it had longer traditions in Staniątki. Taking into account the universal custom of including instruments in the performance of a vocal repertoire already in the 16th century and the fact that in hymnbooks drawn up by Boczkowski we can find the repertoire drawn from the oldest hymnbooks from Staniątki, one may assume that the inclusion of instruments in the performance of a hymn repertoire was practiced already earlier. An additional argument in support of this thesis is the fact that nearly sixty per cent of hymns noted in hymnbook St E contain figures with the lowest part, whereas the use of the organ basso continuo is explicitly marked in the score only in few cases. Figured bass appears also in the oldest 16th century hymns noted in St E, i.a. in the musical settings of *Po upadku człowieka grzesznego* (After the Fall of a Sinful Man), *Urząd zbawienia ludzkiego* (The Office of Human Salvation), *Archanioł Gabriel* (Archangel Gabriel) or *Panie jako jest przedziwne imię Twoje* (Oh Lord, How Extraordinary is Thy Name).

⁵ Cf. [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 145–146].

⁶ St E, leaves 114v–115r.

Figure 3: Hymnbook St E, *Huc omnes qui pugnatis*.

Huc huc omnes Anonim

Canto I
Huc hu[c] om - nes qui pug - na - tis

Canto II

Organo
5 6
3 4
Vio

4
C I
ter - ra mor - tis for - mi - da - tis

C II

Organo
6
Can: Vio 4 3

7
C I
In - vo - ca - te Ma - ri - am con - fu - gi - te con fu - gi - te

C II
In - vo - ca - te Ma - ri - am con - fu - gi - te con fu - gi - te

Organo
7 7 3 3 6 8 7 5 3 6 4

10
C I
ad Ma - ri - am.

C II
ad Ma - ri - am.

Organo
8 9 10 7
6 7 5 4 3 6 7 4 3
Vio

Figure 4: Kazimierz Boczkowski, *Ave sponsa creatoris*, St E, leaf 115r.

Also in the one of the oldest hymnbooks, (St B), we can find an unusually interesting instance of a score notation with figures with a bass-note. The features of this notation substantiate an assumption that it is more likely that the piece was written in the first half of the 17th century.

Figure 5: *Omni die dic Mariae*, St B, leaves 110v–111r.

The composition was written for four parts, marked in the score as “Discant” (Treble), “Alt” (Alto), “Tenor” (Tenor), “Bas” (Bass). In the lowest vocal part appear the figured-bass symbols: 6, in the internal cadence a delay: 5/4 3, 3 flat and 7 6. The notation of the “Bass” part in the C4 clef suggests that it could be performed vocally, whereas the instrumental accompaniment was an additional element. The musical setting of the hymn *Omni die dic Mariae* from the hymnbook St B is the oldest example of a score with figured-bass symbols that we can find in Staniątki. The manner in which in a large part of the compositions contained in the Staniątki hymnbooks the lyrics were written beneath the notes fails to make it easy to reply to the question on the manner of performance of the lowest part. Usually the subsequent verses of the text were written beneath all parts which obviously arose from the will to economize on space and does not necessarily suggest the actual vocal performance of all parts. Only in few cases the score unequivocally indicated the necessity of using an instrument (e.g. in St E, in the hymn *Bądź wesółą Panno czysta* (Be Merry Holy Virgin) beneath the lower stave appears the note “Pro

Organo”). At times, the presence of an accompanying instrument results unequivocally from the arrangement of the score itself where the part of the lowest part was written down twice in clefs F4 (e.g. St E *Martine Sancte Pontifex* or St L *Omnium Sanctorum*). Among all hymns included in the hymnbooks, in over 160 cases (this refers also to the copies of the same composition) the score contains figured-bass — sometimes these are individual symbols which, nonetheless, indicate the presence of the instrument. In the St. Adalbert’s abbey the nuns performing the hymns from the hymnbook used the accompaniment of at least a positive, and, most probably, added also other instruments that could have also doubled the vocal parts. It is interesting insofar as in the case of hymnbooks of the Sandomierz Benedictines,⁷ written down by Zofia Bratysiewiczówna,⁸ there are no premises that would suggest any vocal-instrumental renditions or renditions with the accompaniment of at least the organ continuo. The manner of notation of the lowest part suggests a purely vocal performance — neither figured bass nor symbols indicating the presence of an accompanying instrument can be found.

Coming back to the question of the possible engagement of nuns in the performances of a musical ensemble, let us focus on one more fact. The compositions named thus far that do not raise any major doubts in regard to whether they were performed with the accompaniment of an organ or a positive were included in the hymnbooks. This repertoire was performed by the nuns independently of the liturgy celebrated in the convent church. Henceforth, it is impossible to prove in this context the potential cooperation of secular musicians with the nuns. However, in the hymnbooks notes can also be found that enable — at least in a few cases — to prove that this repertoire was performed during the liturgy. The most obvious example are — admittedly few — fragments of the Mass settings. We can find them in the oldest hymnbooks (A, B, C, D, N) which may mean that in the period preceding the establishment of an ensemble, the nuns enhanced the liturgy merely by singing. The absence of analogous works in the later sources suggests that this role was taken over by an ensemble. A separate case is the hymn *Quem Pastores laudavere*, sung also with the Polish text *Bracia siostry postuchajcie* (Brothers, Sisters, Listen). In the older sources (St A, B) only the lyrics of the hymn are supplied (the melody was popular at that time) suggesting thereby a dramatised performance with a division into four choirs (“Pierwszy Kor” (The First Choir), “Wtóry Kor” (The Second Choir) etc.). There are no data that would authorize an unequivocal statement that in Staniątka — just like in Lvov — that hymn supplied specific interpolations included in “Gloria”, although it is highly likely.⁹ It makes one wonder that in the later sources (St E, F) the hymn was intended to be sung in two parts with the accompaniment of basso continuo, without any division into four choirs (in St E only the entrances of the subsequent parts were marked: “Canto 1mo”, “Canto 2do”). Also the note found in older hymnbooks, regarding the performance of the hymn during the morning Christmas mass (St A: “Czasu Narodzenia Bozego. na pierwszey mszey” (At Christmas Time. At the First Mass.). It is possible that also in this case, in connection with the appearance of a musical ensemble which graced the liturgy, the nuns changed the practice of performing the discussed

⁷ Sandomierz Diocesan Library, call number L 1642.

⁸ On the basis of the analysis of the handwriting the scriptor was identified by Magdalena Walter-Mazur. See [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 215].

⁹ As evidenced by the above-mentioned grumbling of Bishop Radziwiłł.

hymn. It is symptomatic that the above-mentioned, Lvov source provides a confirmation that the nuns in Lvov still in the 18th century included *Quem pastores* in *Gloria*, whereas in Lvov there was no permanent, professional musical ensemble (a Dominican ensemble performed among others at the Benedictines'), although — as Magdalena Walter-Mazur claims — the sisters created a small ensemble all on their own.¹⁰ The most interesting, however, in the context of our deliberations seems to be the note supplied in the hymnbooks St E, H and M by the hymn *Ach królu mój* (Oh, My King). We read there that the hymn “is sung in place of the Offertorium on Flower Sunday” (St E). This means that during a mass celebrated on Palm Sunday (called “Flower Sunday” in the earlier day) the nuns, in place of the *Offertorium*, sang a hymn with the Polish text. What is important, this note appears not only in the hymnbook St E made prior to the establishment of the ensemble (and in hymnbook St H dated for the middle of the century), but also in the hymnbook St M produced in the second half of the 18th century. It implies that even if nuns did not directly participate in the activity of the ensemble itself (which is not excluded), then they sang with the ensemble during liturgy. It sheds a new light on the numerous notes placed most often above the highest part by means of which the possible liturgical uses were marked (e.g. “for Saint Stanislas”). The hymnbooks include also over 40 introits and the musical setting of the text *Asperges me* (St B, C, E, F, G, H, L, N) sung during the *Asperges*, marking the beginning of the mass.

As it has already been mentioned, the hymnbooks of the Sandomierz Benedictines lack the arguments allowing to draw conclusions about the use of the instruments in the interpretations of the hymns, as well as about the performance of this repertoire during the Mass liturgy. It is worthwhile to refer at this point to the information on the repertoire of the hymnbook L 1642, provided in her work by Magdalena Walter-Mazur. The author states that the whole collection contains “79 four-part hymns”,¹¹ which is an imprecise information, to say the least. The collection contains also compositions (fourteen of them) for which only three parts were noted. This reduction in the size of the cast referred mainly to the Christmas repertoire. Interestingly, this mistake is interesting in so far as in a few sentences she discusses one of the three-part compositions, as an example of a particularly interesting setting (*Ave maris stella*),¹². The sources leave no room for doubt that the piece was written for a three-part cast intentionally — in each of the part books it is the second included setting (in the part books marked C1, C2 and B). The continuous manner of notation in book C3 allows us to exclude the possibility of a missing leaf; on f. 3r we have the final part of the piece *Omni di dic Mariae*, whereas on its verso (f. 3v) the next composition has been supplied: *Ave stella matutina*.

It is in order to also briefly refer to the possible ways of transmission of the repertoire and the possible concordancies between the Staniątki and Sandomierz collections. As Walter-Mazur writes:

¹⁰ [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 158–162].

¹¹ [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 215].

¹² [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 215].

“The repertoire links revealed by Trościński¹³ involve exclusively the lyrics. The concordancies and the variants of the melody and its multi-part settings have not been examined. The author pointed out the possibility of transmission of the Staniątki repertoire by the agency of sister Anna Leśniewska who came to Sandomierz in 1682 after a 20-years’ stay in Staniątki or by Kazimierz Michał Boczkowski. However, multi-part settings of analogous hymns included in the Staniątki hymnbooks St E and St F, the copyist whereof was Boczkowski, are intended for three parts (SSB), and not for four, like in the Sandomierz source. Moreover, other hymns from those two hymnbooks with regard to multi-part settings of which Świerczek suggested the authorship by Boczkowski fail to appear in manuscript L 1642”.¹⁴

Table 1 below presents the list of musical settings (versions) from hymnbook L 1642, which are identical or may be treated as variants of compositions included in St E.

The compositions are listed in the same order as in the hymnbook L 1642. We can see that over twenty percent of the repertoire of the Sandomierz hymnbook possesses concordancies in Boczkowski’s hymnbook. This is a significant amount but it does not have to mean that Bratysiewiczówna when writing down the hymnbooks knew or used Boczkowski’s compilation. The consistently sustained assumption by Walter-Mazur about the four parts in the Sandomierz hymnbook leads to subsequent conclusions which can be easily undermined. Namely, it is not true that Boczkowski’s settings for three parts in hymnbook L 1642 are always for four parts — this situation takes place only in three cases. Henceforth, perhaps counter to Magdalena Walter-Mazur’s opinion, and according to Grzegorz Trościński’s line of reasoning, it was exactly Anna Leśniewska who upon the arrival in Sandomierz created the interest of those nuns in the Staniątki repertoire. Let us highlight the fact that without any exceptions the hymns which in Boczkowski’s version were written for three parts, and in the Sandomierz version for four parts we can also find in the oldest hymnbooks, in the part books in Staniątki (St A–D). This means that there need not be a direct dependency between hymnbooks L 1642 and St E, because one of the sources of the Bratysiewiczówna’s compilation may also be older hymnbooks of Staniątki, obviously alongside other, currently unknown sources. It is also worth noting that the reduction in the cast introduced by Boczkowski essentially did not have a negative impact on the quality of the work itself — it did not prevent the writing of quality pieces for three or two parts. By contrast, the analogous reductions that we find in Sandomierz hymnbooks are not always equally fine. An example can be the piece *Martine Sancte Pontifex*, which was written down in St E in a cast for five parts and basso continuo, whereas in L 1642 this cast was reduced to four vocal parts. As a result the work came into being in which (also in terms of the auditive reception) one part is clearly missing.

This gap is particularly felt in measures 10–13, and thereafter in measures 27–31. In Staniątki, the cast reductions used went sometimes much further which is a testimony of the attempts to ‘modernise’ the older, multi-part repertoire. A good example is provided by hymnbook St H, in which 88 hymns were noted in a cast for one high part (clef G2 or C1) or low part (F4) — played

¹³ The author refers to the article of Grzegorz Trościński, dedicated to an analysis of the lyrics[Trościński, 2014].

¹⁴ [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 216].

Table 1: Concordancies between hymnbooks St E and L 1642.

Incipit	No. of voices L 1642	No. of voices St E	Hymnbook St A–D
<i>Ave stella matutina</i>	4	3	+
<i>Gwiazdo morza głębokiego</i> (The Star of the Deep Sea)	3	3	+
<i>Królewnie wiecznej śpiewajmy</i> (Let Us Sing to the Eternal Princess)	4	4	+
<i>O Matko miłościwa</i> (Oh Merciful Mother)	4	3	+
<i>Puer natus in Bethleem</i>	3	3	+
<i>Tobie nad pomysł</i> (To Thou Above the Idea)	4	4	-
<i>Urząd zbawienia ludzkiego</i> (The Office of the Human Salvation)	3	3	+
<i>Witaj Jezu ukochany</i> (Welcome Beloved Jesus)	3	3	+
<i>Ziemia ożyła</i> (The Earth Came Alive)	3	3	-
<i>Ave magne Rex caelorum</i>	3	3	+
<i>Catharine virginis laudes</i>	4	5+bc	-
<i>Każde stworzenie śpiewaj</i> (Thou Shalt Sing, Every Creature)	4	4/3	+
<i>Martine Sancte Pontifex</i>	4	5+bc	+
<i>Nicolai solemnna</i>	4	4	+
<i>O Jezu jakoś ciężko skatowany</i> (Oh Jesus, How Gravely Injured Art Thou)	4	4	+
<i>Veni Creator Spiritus</i>	4	3	+
<i>Salve cordis gaudium</i>	3	3	-

Figure 6: *Martine Sancte Pontifex*, measures 6–15, St E, L 1642.

The image displays two systems of musical notation for the piece *Martine Sancte Pontifex*, measures 6–15, St E, L 1642. Each system consists of five staves: a vocal line (Soprano) and four instrumental parts (Violin I, Violin II, Viola, and Cello/Double Bass). The music is written in a key signature of one flat (B-flat major or D minor) and a common time signature (C). The notation includes various note values, rests, and accidentals, with some notes beamed together. The first system covers measures 6 through 10, and the second system covers measures 11 through 15. The vocal line features a melodic line with some grace notes and a final cadence. The instrumental parts provide harmonic support with sustained notes and rhythmic patterns.

probably on a positive (or on an organ). A large part of hymns written down in this cast possesses their multi-part equivalents in older hymnbooks – e.g. St E *Bądź wesola Panno czysta* (Be Merry, Pure Virgin) (C1, C4, F4, F4), *Largum Vesper* enjoying a major popularity in Staniątki (St E, F, L: C1, C1, C3, C4, F4), or *Salve parvule dzieciątko dostojne* (Salve parvule, Honourable Child) (St F, L: C1, C1/C2, C4, F4). Interestingly, also the cast of pieces for a low number of parts was reduced, e.g. *Asperges me* (in St E, L: C1, C1, F4) or a hymn composed by Boczkowski *Och drogie perły* (Oh, Dear Pearls) (in St E: C1, C1, F4). It may thus be well-grounded to advance a thesis that as an outcome of the appearance of a vocal-instrumental ensemble, the nuns assumed less responsibility themselves for the shape of the musical framework of the liturgy which may have had an impact on the departure from a multi-part repertoire for the benefit of an easier to perform solo singing with an accompaniment. However, it needs to be noted that in the late sources (even in the discussed hymnbook St H) there are settings written for three or more parts. It appears thus that indicating the dependency between the setting up of an ensemble and the possible lower standard of the nuns' singing would be a major oversimplification. The tendency to reduce this cast is rather a manifestation of the general trends, namely the resignation from polyphony for the benefit of a homophonic texture. Thus, Stanisław Dąbek rightly notices that the reduction in the number of parts was not a permanent phenomenon, reflecting some kind of a regression. The increase of this phenomenon can be observed within individual hymnbooks.¹⁵ On this occasion, it is worth referring to the provided cast statistics of the multi-part hymns in the context of the performance of the lowest part on the organ. Dąbek provided a figure of 96 multi-part hymns in a vocal cast with an organ accompaniment and 45 parts in a vocal cast.¹⁶ While commenting upon the above list he stated that “If we were to bind the lowest, non-figured part with the organ accompaniment — in line with the European tendency [...] — then the ratio would increase for the benefit of this type of a cast”.¹⁷ It seems that a hypothesis about the decisive domination of the above type of a cast may be emphasised even more strongly by assuming that in the majority of the cases the lowest part was performed instrumentally. The above-mentioned case of the hymn *Omni die dic Mariae* indicates that even if the texture of the lowest part fell within the range achievable for the nuns, it sometimes was performed on the organ. Also indirect sources confirm this practice — the easy to observe care about the condition of the organ (observed throughout the centuries but at least since the middle of the 16th century) and the presence of a professional organist leave no doubt that this instrument played an essential role in the musical life of the convent.

2 Musical ensemble

Organisation of a musical ensemble at the order of prioress Małachowska in 1750 opens a new chapter in the history of music of the Staniątki convent. Unfortunately, little information directly concerned with the ensemble and its activity has been preserved in the sources. There are, for

¹⁵ [Dąbek, 1997, 93].

¹⁶ [Dąbek, 1997, 95].

¹⁷ [Dąbek, 1997, 96].

instance, no documents that regulate the relations between the convent and the musicians that we know from other centres of monastic life (e.g. Jasna Góra).¹⁸ Also the foundation act of the ensemble has not survived until our times — if it ever existed at all. Henceforth, the main source of our knowledge about the ensemble and the musicians who were active in it are the convent’s account ledgers. They do not cover the full period of the Staniątki ensemble’s activity which, according to the preserved sources, covered the whole, nearly 100-years’ long period from 1759 until 1849. Particularly troublesome is the lack of ledgers from the year when the ensemble was disbanded — an analysis of expenditures from that period could perhaps enable the indication of the direct reasons for the resignation from the maintenance of a permanent ensemble. Fortunately, we possess the account records from the year the ensemble was established owing to which we may find that the decision of prioress Małachowska came in reply to the growing needs of the community. It needs to be underlined that the convent in Staniątki maintained the ensemble at a particularly difficult time when historical disasters entailed a significant impoverishment of the convent. Let us then have a closer look at the account ledgers from the examined period.

In Staniątki no separate ledgers were kept of the musical ensemble and the expenditures related to music were included in other abbey maintenance costs. The oldest of the preserved account ledgers comes from the years 1712–1720.¹⁹ At this time — as Bogusław Krasnowolski notes²⁰ — under the rule of prioress Teresa Niewiarowska the economic situation of the convent improved. It seems that the musical life of the convent in the first quarter of the 18th century was mainly focused around the sung *Officium* and the hymn repertoire. Eight hymnbooks from Staniątki come from the 18th century, including E and F written down by organist Kazimierz Boczkowski. Boczkowski held the function of an organist in 1700–1709. Perhaps his direct successor was Jakub Surnikowski, who — next to the probably related cantor, Marcin Surnikowski — is named in the convent chronicle on the occasion of the organ’s overhaul in 1721. Among the expenditures in the years 1713–1720 we find only few records related to the convent’s musical life. What is important, these records prove unequivocally that the only permanently employed musician at that time was the organist (he was the only person who received the so-called “suchedni” – ‘per diems’). There is no written record of any activity of a cantor, although in the later years these two functions were clearly distinguished from each other. Perhaps, at that time, the organist combined two functions or the convent constrained itself to maintaining only the organist because one of the nuns played the role of a cantor whereas a separate position was created in the period preceding the aforementioned overhaul. The convent needed also a “kalikant” (a person handling the bellows of a pipe organ), which was not a permanent function, generating permanent income. In the discussed period, a “kalikant” received no remuneration, and only irregularly received 3 zloty for the purchase of shoes.²¹ On the other hand, the organist received a quarterly remuneration which amounted to 20 zloty, although there were delays, like

¹⁸ *Acta Conventus Clari Montis Czestochoviensis*, The Archives of the Pauline Fathers on Jasna Góra, call number AJG 196.

¹⁹ PL-STAb, *Reiestr pinedzy...* (Register of Money...), inv. 674, top. 848.

²⁰ [Krasnowolski, 1999, 191].

²¹ In the account ledgers of 1713-1720 this payment appears in the years: 1713, 1715, 1717, 1718, 1719 and 1720.

for instance in 1719 when he received a lumpsum of 80 zloty (“the held per diems gave the organist 80 zloty”), and earlier only 10 zloty paid in March. No doubt that the earnings amounting to ca. 80 zł per year need to be considered relatively low and, therefore, this ruled out the possibility of living only by organ playing.

Unfortunately, the books from 1720–1748 are missing which makes it impossible to draw the picture of musical life in that period. The next existing written records come from the years 1748–1750.²² In the meantime major changes must have taken place because the structure of expenditures the convent spent on musicians is completely different. Most certainly, the revival in this respect was caused by the founding of the new organ. Its creator was Michał Krzemycki of Tuchowo who rebuilt the instrument in the Wawel Cathedral [Prus, 1975, 101] in 1720–1727. As we can read in the chronicle:

“A.D. 1721. The work of the organ came into being [...] at the expense of Prioress, Katarzyna Teresa Niewiarowska and Miss Housekeeper Zofia Gościmieńska [...] by the work and execution of Michał Krzemycki of Tuchowo. By the agency of Reverend Jakob Cichoński, the nuns’ confessor — during the reign of king August II. At that time [...] the organist was Jakób Surnikowski, and the cantor Marcin Surnikowski [...]”²³

A clear sign that the convent attached an ever growing importance to the music for the liturgy was the raise for the organist and the permanent position for the cantor. In the years 1748–1750, the organist received regular quarterly payments in the amount of 26 zloty (an increase by over 20 per cent compared to the first half of the 18th century), whereas the cantor received 21 zloty.

The fundamental question that remains is the exact foundation date of the permanent musical ensemble. This question brings us to another one, and, namely, whether in Staniątki — as it was the case in many smaller centres — the establishment of an ensemble was the outcome of a longer process or was of a sudden nature, resulting from the mere fact of the foundation. It is known that the ensemble was called to life by the decision of prioress Katarzyna Małachowska who held its function in 1729–1753.²⁴ The information about the establishment of the ensemble is provided in the *Regestr siostr...* (Register of Nuns...)²⁵ of 1760. In the biogramme of prioress Małachowska we read:

“Whereas dedicated to the perpetual praising of God, enriched the Foundation with 4 musicians with various instruments so that the Glory of God would sound and allocated a salary to them. Because there was only the organist and the cantor. A.D. 1750”.

²² PL-STAb, Expensa, inv. 677, top. 214.

²³ *Kronika klasztoru staniąteckiego za czasów P.X.Z.L. Baryszewskiej. Na imieniny zebrana z dawnych kronik klasztornych* (The Chronicle of the Staniątki Convent from the Times of P.X.Z.L. Baryszewska. Collected from Old Convent chronicles to mark Her Name’s Day), vol. I, inv. 208, top. 721.

²⁴ Cf. [Krasnowolski, 1999, 148–159].

²⁵ PL-STAb, *Regestr siostr...*, inv. 552, top. 222.

This laconic note caused that the later scholars adopted the year 1750 as a dividing line between the two periods in the history of the convent.²⁶ Meanwhile, the already conducted research helps to shed a new light on the process of creation of a professional musical ensemble in Staniątki. The first characteristic proof that the decision about the establishment of the ensemble matured for at least a few years are the ‘per diem’ records of 1748–1749. Alongside the abovementioned payments for the organist and the cantor, we can find there seven records which read: “For the Old Organist who teaches the boy to sing 5 Złó”. The remuneration was paid throughout the whole 1748 and three quarters of 1749. Because the sources are missing we do not know whether the process of teaching the singer started already before 1748.

Of course, this mere fact does not unequivocally prove that efforts were undertaken to establish a professional ensemble. However, if we put it in a broader context, one may assume that that was the goal of employing a retired organist. The expenditures made at that time for the musical setting of the services may be divided into several basic categories. One of them were the costs of employing foreign ensembles; we have at least eight such visits documented in the years 1748–1750. In 1748, Staniątki was visited by a Jesuit ensemble (most probably from Cracow) which received quite a high fee (in February 1748 it was 36 zł). Quite frequently, the Benedictine nuns hosted also an ensemble from the nearby Niegowić (among others, in January and March 1749, and in January and April 1750). The ensemble received a fee within the range of 18–20 zł (without counting one-off Christmas carroll performances for which it received from 5 to 8 zł). It means that it was the wish of prioress Małachowska to enhance particularly important celebrations (such as the feast of St Benedict, St Adalbert or the Benedictine saints) by means of a professional musical setting. The above mentioned category of expenditures includes also less clear records, such as “Ensemble for S. Woyciey [sic!]”. We do not know whether a reference is made to an external ensemble or the convent’s own musicians (and such notes appear already in 1748). The most intriguing, however, is another category of expenditures, namely the sums allocated to ‘sacristians’. Of course, the first association that comes to mind is the church official taking care of the organisation of religious services. Instead, already on January 4, 1748 in the book of ‘expenses’ we clearly read: “For Sacristians for the Founder’s Day who played at the Holy Mass Złoty 3 [gr] 16”. Even more unequivocally the role of ‘sacristians’ was described on March 14, 1749: “For Sacristians who played and sang at the Holy Mass Złó 6”. In 1748 itself we can find as many as 14 such performances. Any doubts whether we can talk here about local musicians or whether the name ‘sacristian’ was used also for external musicians is dispelled by a record of August 18, 1749: “For Exequies for Sister Domagalska [...] for Sacristians both local and visiting Złó 8”. The records about the fees paid to musicians indicate that we can talk with a high dose of probability about a small, local musical ensemble active in Staniątki at least from the beginnings of 1748 (and probably also earlier than that). While external ensembles received amounts in the order of 20 złoty (or more), local musicians received ca. 3 zł. The fee amounts reflect also a steady professionalization of the ensemble, and probably also its enlargement. Already on August 15, for the Feast of the Assumption, the ensemble received 11 zł, whereas on November 25, 1749 for the feast of St Catherine it received 8 zł.

²⁶ Cf. [Krasnowolski, 1999, 190], [Maciejewski, 1984, 18], [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 270].

Also other expenditures reflect the attempts made to set up an ensemble already in 1749. In June and November of that year the convent spent certain amounts (each time slightly over 2 zł) for a hat and shoes for the “Boy Singer”. In turn, on March 12, 1750, a boy’s robe’ (“Kontusik”) was bought for the same boy. One may assume that in as much as the purchase of shoes and the hat for the young singer was not a binding expenditure yet (at that time the Benedictine nuns used to support the poor with higher amounts), the purchase of a robe can already be treated as an investment.²⁷ One more intriguing item on the list of expenditures is the amount of 2 zł and 16 gr described as “For the cantor from Cracow for the road”. It is likely that this visit was somehow linked with the organisation of the ensemble, although it is of course sheer conjecture.

In the light of the above information it is worth attempting a more precise determination of the time when prioress Małachowska created a musical ensemble. A lot indicates that this moment could be the middle of 1750. In April that year, to mark the feast of St. Adalbert an ensemble from Niegowić played host. However, it was the last such record. Although in the previous years the convent invited ensembles for the November service in honour of the Benedictine saints, nonetheless in 1750 such a record is missing. It makes one wonder why musicians of the Staniątki ensemble were not on the ‘per diem’ pay roll, if — provided we are to believe the records included in the Regestr²⁸ — those were four musicians with ‘various’ instruments. The whole of 1750 only the organist and the cantor receive salaries (26 and 21 zł, respectively). Most probably in the first years of its activity the ensemble was quite loosely organised, and enhanced only more important celebrations. This would explain the information from the Regestr that before 1750 in Staniątki there was only “the organist and the cantor”. There are no reasons to undermine the adopted date of the ensemble’s establishment in 1750. Nonetheless, one should read the above statement with a grain of salt. The accounting records leave no room for doubt that — although in a less organised form — a half-amateur musical ensemble must have already functioned in Staniątki before. In this context it is important to note that in the period directly preceding the establishment of the ensemble the account ledgers provide no records of expenditures for instruments. The nuns were extremely conscientious with putting down all the costs connected with the maintenance of the convent. Thus, it would be at least surprising if the cost of purchase of the instruments which was not small, were not included. In the later periods each of the investments of this type was conscientiously put down. We may thus assume that the instruments were bought most probably still before 1748.

The composition of the ensemble in the second half of the 18th century did not undergo any major changes. According to the premises laid down by prioress Małachowska those were usually four musicians who at least since 1755²⁹ were on the convent’s pay roll (‘per diems’). In the years 1755, 1761–62 the convent employed four musicians (“For Per Diems to Four Musicians”) and the organist and the cantor who received a remuneration in the amount of 32 zł (i. e. 8 zł each,

²⁷ We do not, unfortunately, know the exact cost of the robe (Polish: kontusz), because in the same column the purchase of a skirt for “Przekrzcianka” (A Convert from Judaism) is entered. In total, the convent spent 36 zloty on these items.

²⁸ PL-STAb, inv. 552, top. 222.

²⁹ From this moment onwards the expenses are recorded in the account ledgers. The *Expensy* (Expenses) from the years 1750–1755 are missing.

unless, as the later practice shows, these weren't equal salaries). Thereafter, in the years 1777–78, 1780–86, 1788–89, there were only three of them, not counting the organist and the cantor. For a brief period, towards the end of 1783, the composition of the ensemble was extended again to four persons, and, in January 1784, it was reduced again to only three musicians. More serious amounts in the composition of the ensemble took place only in the beginning of the 19th century, which shall be discussed in a greater detail later on.

In the discussed period the salaries of the musicians were steady and amounted to the mentioned 8 zł. In total, this gave the amount of 32 zł annually, without counting the additional income for playing during funerals, feasts, Christmas caroll services and rare situations when the convent supported its musicians by paying their debts,³⁰ paying for their clothes and shoes or helping them to pay for their other needs. A spectacular example of this type of care for the musicians was the exorbitant — as for an average remuneration — amount of one thousand zloty that one ensemble member, Paweł Dynowski, received (or borrowed — the source does not clearly state this) on February 23, 1804.³¹

Figure 7: “Suchedni” (‘Per Diems’), May 1755 (PL-STAb, inv. 678, top. 216, p. 18)

26	Ła Suchedni MGi Xiedru Spowiednikowi	90
	Na dwóch Kapelanow na suchedni	120
	Organiscie Kantowowi na suchedni	52
	Cityrem Murzhanom	32
	Siwowawowi	8
	Bednarowi	5
	Stychurzowi	5
	Drzewnikowi	5

By way of an example, in 1762 the convent spent 656 zloty in total (including 126 for the purchase of instruments) for the needs of the ensemble. If we deduct the ‘per diems’ of the cantor and the organist, we shall obtain an average amount of 79 zł for one musician, taking into account that in this year there were four of them. The remuneration equalled more or less the amount that a Staniatki organist received in the first quarter of the 18th century and it sufficed only for a very modest life. It comes thus as no surprise that the members of the ensemble did also

³⁰ E.g. in April 1798 the convent spent the amount of 80 zł “Organiscie dług zakupiony karczmy” (For the Organist’s debt in the inn.)

³¹ “Kapeliscie Pawłowi Dynowskiemu na Drzewo na Dom y rozne potrzeby do tegoz 1000” (To Musician Paweł Dynowski for wood, house and his various needs in it – 1000), PL-STAb, *Reiestr Widatkow...* (Register of Expenditures...), inv. 686, top. 723.

additional jobs in the convent that were not directly related to their main function.³² Perhaps for this reason, particularly in the initial period of the ensemble’s activity, the account ledgers do not call it ‘an ensemble’, and use a broader concept of ‘sacristians’ instead. Some doubts in regard to the manner in which the nuns entered the amounts spent on music are the outcome of the laconic nature of some entries. Throughout the discussed period, the category that is encountered very often are expenditures “for the Mass”. A question comes to mind whether these not very high amounts (usually ca. 2–4 zł) are not a pay for musicians accompanying the services. However, if we compare the costs of an ‘ordinary’ mass with the costs characteristic for services held with a more elaborate musical setting, the difference will be very clear. Admittedly, it happened that these costs were similar but mainly in a situation when the musical setting was provided only by the organist and the cantor.³³ When the ensemble size increased, the costs were proportionally higher.³⁴

Figure 8: The Expenditures of the Convent for Music in the First Half of the 18th Century.

Table 8 shows us a list of expenditures that can be classified as related to the convent’s musical life in the first half of the 18th century. We can see that they grew radically towards the end of

³² E.g. A certain Hazoski (vel Charzowski) in the years 1780, 1784, 1788–80, 1792 and 1798 received 30 zł for “Nakręcanie Zygara” (Winding up the Clock), whereas Józef Cichaski (cantor, copyist) painted the church and other monastic interiors or baked wafers.

³³ In June 1761 “Za Litanie Organiscie y Kantorowi co grawali przez Dziewięć wTorkow [sic!]” (For the Litany to the Organist and the Cantor who played for nine tuesdays [sic!]) the convent paid 9 zł. *Reiestr Expensy...* (Register of Expenses...), inv. 676, top. 203.

³⁴ E.g. on March 21, 1755 the convent paid 18 zł “Muzykantom za Msze y Nieszpory na S. O. Benedykt” (To Musicians for the Mass and Vespers for the feast of St Benedict). Let us remember that at that time the full line-up consisted of four musicians, the cantor and the organist. The “Kalikant” is not included in the composition because he received his fee separately.

this period. While in the first quarter the convent spent for its annual purposes ca. 80 zł,³⁵ in 1748 this amount was nearly six times higher and reached as much as 477 zł. It is worth noting that 25 per cent of this amount were expenditures for the services of external ensembles because the term ‘ensemble’ in this context most probably refers to musicians from outside Staniątki (e.g. “Kapeli co byli na Wszystkich Świętych Zakonu naszego” (Ensemble that was on the All Saints; of our convent). The costs of hiring an external ensemble were incommensurably high. In the abovementioned 1748 the ensemble was paid once 36 zł (“Dla Xiędza Jezuity co był z kapelą” – For Reverend Jesuit who came with an ensemble). In the meantime, local ‘sacristians’ received barely 10 zloty for the singing of a litany throughout the entire Lent (“Koscielnym za Litanie S Jozefa przez cały post” – To Sacristians for the Litany of St Joseph throughout the entire Lent). There is thus no doubt that one of the reasons why prioress Małachowska decided to set up a permanent musical ensemble was of economic nature. Already in 1750 it brought visible effects because for those “guest” performances the nuns paid 62 zł in total, i.e. one half less compared to the year 1748. Unfortunately, the lack of data for 1721–1748 does not allow us to indicate at what specific time the ‘sacristians’ appeared in the church, as well as whether there was a surge in expenditures for musical purposes. This period coincides with the reign of prioress Teresa Niewiarowska (1712–1728),³⁶ the short period when Zuzanna Jordanówna held the office (d. 1729), and the times of her successor, Katarzyna Małachowska (d. 1753). Niewiarowska took over the management of the convent at a difficult time when the 3rd Northern War (1700–1721) rolled across the country and the lands of the Commonwealth of Both Nations were plundered by foreign armies (which did not fail to omit Staniątki). The chronicler Anna Kiernicka wrote about these events as follows:

“Dopuścił Pan Bóg straszną plagę karania swego na całą Polskę, kiedy stała się mieyscem pełnym nieprzyjaciół, iako to Szwedów, Sasów, Moskali, a co większa y sami Synowie Oyczyzny rozdzielwszy się na partye, kray własny niszczyli, jęczały pod ciemieniem, rabunkami, kontrybucyami y Senatorskie Dobra, a coż duchownych y Panienskie, opłacała Panna Xieni Stocka [ksieni w latach 1688–1712] do pokiey mogła, wreszcie w wielkie zaszła długi [...]” (Lord allowed the horrible plague of his punishment into whole Poland when it became a place full of enemies, Swedes, Saxons, Moscovites, and, what is more, the Sons of our Fatherland, having divided into parties, destroyed their own country, under the oppression, plundering, contributions also Senators’ goods moaned, so what to speak of Maidens’. Prioress Stocka [the

³⁵ A bigger amount in 1713 resulted from paying an outstanding remuneration: “organiscie zatrzymanych szuchedni razem dała złotych 100 50 [150]” (I gave the withheld per diems to an organist – 100 50 [150]). Very peculiar is the convention of noting down the figures by the convent scriptor who entered the figures in the account ledger at that time. Writing down hundreds and tens separately may cause some confusion. In this case, however, there is no doubt because writing down the amount of 50 gr would not make any sense because the amount equalled 1 zł and 20 gr. Moreover, each time when the scriptor wanted to mark that she meant “grosze”, she preceded the figure with the letter ‘g’. Eventually, any doubts are resolved by the entry of June 24, 1713 where it is written: “za Jagły złotych 100 5 g 10” (For Jagły zloty 100 5 g 10). PL-STAb, *Reiestr pinedzy...* (Register of Money...) inv. 674, top. 848.

³⁶ [Krasnowolski, 1999, 148].

prioress in the years 1688-1712] paid as long as she could, and, finally, ran into big debts [...]).³⁷

The outcome of the convent's economic problems was the debt mentioned by Kiernicka which — if we are to believe the anniversary books — soared to 70, 000 zł.³⁸ Prioress Niewiarowska not only managed to pay all the debts, but also carried out an overhaul of the monastery and built a new organ. It seems unlikely that the convent could afford additional expenditures connected with the maintenance of an ensemble. It is also hard to assume that after a nearly annual period of the reign of Zuzanna Jordanówna any activity was undertaken in this area. The prioress herself was aware of her advanced age (the moment she was elected she was at least 70 years old) and she probably did not embark on any dynamic activity.³⁹ It is thus most likely that the efforts to form an ensemble were started in the beginnings of the reign of prioress Małachowska. The first instrumentalists must have thus appeared in the thresholds of the convent in the period between 1730 and mid 1740s.

Figure 9: The Expenditures of the Convent for Music in the Second Half of the 18th Century and in the Beginning of the 19th Century

³⁷ Anna Kiernicka, *Dzieje klasztorne od fundacji aż dotąd...* (Monastic History from the Foundation until Today...), inv. 203, top. 705. p. 119.

³⁸ This amount is supplied in the anniversary book of 1778–1843. PL-STAb, inv. 553, top. 710, p. 6.

³⁹ As we can read in the Chronicle authored by Sister Antonina Scholastyka Kaładulska, when she was elected she reportedly joked: “A teraz cóż stąd za korzyść, tak dla mnie jako i wam, kiedy już półtrupem” (And what good will come of it to me and to you if I am already half-dead). PL-STAb, inv. 207, top. 720, p. 83.

Figure 10: Expenditures and Revenue of the Dominican ensemble in the Corpus Christi convent in Lvov in 1761-1765. (Revenue – blue, expenditures – red).

The structure of expenditures for the musical life⁴⁰ is illustrated in Table 9. It says that already within the first five years of the ensemble’s official activity, the convent increased the means appropriated for music during the services. The Staniątki nuns must have got used to the sound of the instruments in their church since they were ready to bear these costs. To get a broader picture, let us compare the table 9 with the table of expenditures and revenue of the ensemble of the Lvov Dominicans from the Corpus Christi convent from 1761–65 (table 10).⁴¹ At that time Dominicans did separate accounting for an ensemble and, in addition, it did not cover ‘per diems’ a separate record of which was kept. The Dominican ensemble had a much more elaborate line-up, nonetheless, the expenditures recorded in the said manuscript more or less correspond with the categories included in the Staniątki account ledgers. It means that the funds appropriated by the nuns for the ensemble did not diverge greatly from those expended in other centres. It is worth noting that the Dominican ensemble generated significant revenue from being hired by other Lvov-based monasteries. Throughout most of the period that is recorded in the preserved sources, these earnings (added to the convent’s finances) covered the current costs of the ensemble’s activity in total. Meanwhile, the Staniątki sources are silent about any profits flowing from making an ensemble available to other centres. In the numerous account ledgers no mention can be found of ‘lending’ the musicians. This means that — which is likely — while musicians played also outside the monastery, they did it on their own account, although certainly without any detriment to the duties towards the convent.

⁴⁰ We include in this category the ‘per diems’ for musicians (including the organist and the cantor), the costs of the musical setting of the services, Christmas caroll services, accidental expenditures (such as the purchase of shoes) and the remuneration of the “kalikant”.

⁴¹ The Archives of the Polish Province of the Dominicans in Cracow, call no. Lw 57.

What's essential, in 1755 the amount of 510 zł was used up entirely for the needs of local musicians.⁴² In 1761 it was 527 zł, and in the next year, 1762, it was 656 zł. Alas, we do not possess data for the years 1756–61 and 1763–76. Helpful, however, is the knowledge about the general situation of the abbey in that period. The years 1753–1772 were the reign of prioress Marianna Józefa Jordanówna that were the period of economic stabilisation and numerous investments.⁴³ There is no doubt that next to the funds for the construction work, money for the ensemble has also been found. In the *Regestr...* (Register...) we read that Jordanówna “[...] Bibliotekę Księgami nowemi, ile możność ieý býła założýła. Książ troie do Churowego Spiwánia, Nowo po Opráwiać kázała” (Provided the Library with new books as far as possible. She had three books for choral singing bound).⁴⁴ It is at her order that new instruments were bought for the ensemble, which took place on April 5, 1762: “Za Walterny dwie y Trąby dwie [zł] 126 [...] Za Musztuk [zł] 7” (For two French horns and two trumpets 126 [zł] [...] For a mouthpiece 7 [zł]). It is a very valuable piece of information because as a matter of fact there are no other premises enabling to define the instrumental composition of the ensemble in that period. Another valuable testimony is the oldest of the preserved manuscripts in the collections that remained after the ensemble being the Trio B–major by Carl Philipp Emanuel Bach given to the convent in 1764.

It is doubtful whether the gift would be donated to a convent not possessing the instruments allowing to perform the work. The violin was certainly at the disposal of the ensemble although no information can be found about their purchase (which could, of course, have taken place in the period the account ledgers are silent of), it is known that the nuns played this instrument. At that time, among others, sister Franciszka Szachowiczówna stayed in Staniątki and she could play the flute and the violin.⁴⁵ Perhaps it was her who, together with one of the other nuns, played this instrument on January 28, 1749 for which she received 4 zł: “Pannom Mistrzynom obiema za Oracye Zł 16 [...] Co grały na Skrzypcach Zł 4” (To Two Sisters for Orations 16 Zł [...] To those who played the violin 4 zł).⁴⁶

Coming back to the issue of sums appropriated for the needs of musical life in the discussed period, it may be assumed with a high degree of certainty that in the period of economic stabilisation which started during the reign of prioress Niewiarowska lasted until the Bar Confederation (1768–1772), the funds for the maintenance of the ensemble were also secured. The five-year period (1756–1760) from which unfortunately no financial data have been preserved, is the time of enhanced efforts for the beautification of the church's interior. It is then that the main altar is built (1759). From the same period comes also the polychromy (1760) and the altar of the Holy Cross.⁴⁷ The music played during the services at that time was a perfect addition to the just Baroque-ised interior of the Church.

⁴² Only on Christmas Eve 4 zł were spent on wafers brought by organists from Niepołomice, Brzezcie and Grabie. PL-STAb, *Reiestr expensy...* (Register of expenses...) inv. 678, top. 216.

⁴³ Cf. [Krasnowolski, 1999, 150].

⁴⁴ PL-STAb, *Regestr...* (Register...) inv. 552, top. 222, p. 66.

⁴⁵ Cf. [Szylar, 2015].

⁴⁶ PL-STAb, *Expensa...* (Expenses...), inv. 677, top. 214.

⁴⁷ Cf. [Krasnowolski, 1999, 150].

Figure 11: C. Ph. E. Bach, Trio B–major, title page, call no. 12b.

Ad Maiorem Dei ^{N 12} ~~Gloriam~~ ^h

Trio ex B. #

Violino^{mo}

Violino^{do}

et

Basso Excelente

Con Organo

Dell' sig. Bach.

un poco
Andante

Ta szkła z Wielki Polski o ~~Wielki~~ Cielca
Szachowicza

Konwentu Jani ~~Janickiego~~ Roku 1764
Dawowana

N 12

We are, unfortunately, not in possession of any data that would allow us to draw conclusions on the repertoire performed then by the convent ensemble. However, taking into account a large number of concordancies between the Staniątki hymnbooks and the repertoire of hymnbooks of the Benedictine nuns from Sandomierz, as well as the fact that the organist and the composer Kazimierz Boczkowski prior to his arrival in Staniątki stayed in Sandomierz, it may be presumed that the exchange of the repertoire between the Benedictine convents was lively. As Barbara Przybyszewska-Jarmińska writes:

“The flow of repertoire between the monasteries and convents of the same rule, and, sometimes, of different rules, was a widespread phenomenon at that time. This affected not only liturgical books but also the contemporary one- and multi-part repertoire, mainly of religious, but also of secular nature, the perfect example being organ tablatures from Oliwa, made by a Cistercian monk linked with the monastery in Oliwa, but written down to a major extent during his stay in the Jesuit college in Braniewo”.⁴⁸

On having a closer look at the preserved repertoire from the collections of the Diocesan Library in Sandomierz, *per analogiam* cautious hypotheses may be put forward in regard to the repertoire of the Staniątki ensemble at that time. Of the 128 manuscripts having a Benedictine convent provenance (as Magdalena Walter-Mazur claims),⁴⁹ mainly from Sandomierz, 36 compositions are arias, whereas 52 are vocal-instrumental concertos. Among them we shall find two concertos by Boczkowski: *Prosa de Spiritu Sancto a 9*⁵⁰ and *Concerto de Resurrectione D.N.J.C. Christus resurgens ex mortuis*.⁵¹

Particularly this second composition seems interesting on account of the cast and dating (1700 being the year when Boczkowski started to work in Staniątki). On the title leaf of this manuscript an interesting note reads: “Klaryny na skrzypcach grać trzeba” (Clarini need to be played on the violin). As Magdalena Walter-Mazur writes about the above note:

“This information was written down on one of the oldest preserved vocal-instrumental pieces, on the title leaf of *Concerto de resurrectione* by Kazimierz Boczkowski, dated for 1700. However, on the final leaf of the manuscript beneath the organ part is an inscription: ‘Tubes should be tuned to the higher Delasolre (...)’ proving that the part of the trumpets was played also on *tromba marina*. The parts of trumpets and French horns in the 2nd half of the century could sometimes be played by paid trumpet-players. Who, however, played the parts of the oboe or the flute? Due to the texture and the register they could certainly be played on the violin”.⁵²

In Staniątki perhaps such changes were practised at the time of Boczkowski’s activity, although we do not have e.g. any data to assume that the nuns used *tuba marina*. The information we possess on the composition and the instruments played by the ensemble around mid 18th

⁴⁸ [Przybyszewska-Jarmińska, 2006] [electronic edition].

⁴⁹ [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 244].

⁵⁰ Sandomierz Diocesan Library, call no. 145/A VII 5, scoring: CATB, 2vl, 2clni, vne, org.

⁵¹ Sandomierz Diocesan Library, call no. 244/A VII, scoring: 2C B, 2 clni, org.

⁵² [Walter-Mazur, 2014, 156–157].

Figure 12: Kazimierz Boczkowski, *Prosa de Spiritu Sancto*, title page.

century allow us to assume that during the services the ensemble could play specifically such a repertoire, i.e. church arias and concerts. A quite obvious question that comes to mind is whether apart from the preserved manuscripts containing vocal-instrumental music there were any other sources, and if yes then what happened to them. A major part of the preserved musical sources that remained after the ensemble comes from the end of the 18th century and the first quarter of the 19th century. Their making is linked with the activity of Józef Cichaski who was the most active copyist in Staniątki. The fact of the ensemble's reorganisation, enhancement of its instrumental composition at the time when Cichaski was the cantor and the organist is confirmed by the sources themselves, as well as by the available data on the instruments. In the inventory of 1766 we can find information which says that at that time the ensemble had at its disposal: a viola, four trumpets, two horns ("Walterni dwie" – two French horns) and kettledrums.⁵³ Half a century later, according to the inventory made in 1807,⁵⁴ this composition was incomparably greater. In the said inventory we can read about the trumpets as follows: "Trąb starych niezdatnych do Użycia potrzebując Reparacyi" (Old trumpets, unfit for use, require a repair) — this information refers probably to the instruments listed in the inventory of 1766. It may thus be assumed with a high degree of probability that in the early stages of its activity the ensemble was composed mainly of trumpet-players and singers. While considering the possible repertoire performed in Staniątki in the first half of the 18th century, we should take into account a few notable facts. Boczkowski, upon arriving in the convent in 1700, possessed already good skills as a composer and was prepared to conduct a reorganisation of musical life. Despite this, his activity focused on collecting older hymn repertoire and adding new compositions of this type. What is more, his hymnbook soon gained copies. This means that the tradition of hymnbook singing at that time was still alive and — given the lack of other sources — it may be assumed that the nuns performed hymns not only (as the bishop's reforms recommended) outside the liturgy, but also during it. Save for bigger feasts when external ensembles were invited, those were the nuns who had to take responsibility for the music played during the services held in the church. It is hard to explain the lack of other types of repertoire in the Staniątki collection. Obviously, the tempestuous history and random incidents (such as the fire of Jasna Góra which ended in a loss of nearly the entire repertoire of the ensemble from the 17th century) more often than not led to the destruction of the musical collections. However, Staniątki, against the background of many other centres, stands out not only because of its great care for musical heritage, but also because it luckily avoided random events, such as a fire. The nuns held the musical and other manuscripts with utmost care which is evidenced not only by the state of their preservation, but also the notes that we find in many manuscripts. For instance in Reformationes in the place where a few leaves were torn out, an indignant nun wrote:

"Ktara tu y co wydarła musi się zprawić Panu Bogu [...]. Wszak upadki y karania iednych, są przestroga y lekarstwem dla drugich. Nie iest złe Niebo choc w nim zgrzeszył lucyper, y tak wiele zgorszył innych. Magdalena S. nie wstydzi sie w Niebie

⁵³ PL-STAb, *Inwentarz kościoła i klasztoru z roku 1766* (Inventory of the Church and the Convent of 1766), inv. 648 top. 220.

⁵⁴ PL-STAb, List of instruments of 1807, a loose leaf in a portfolio of documents, inv. 651 top. A 165.

ze ią do tąd na ziemi grzesnicą zowią”⁵⁵ (The one who tore out something here must rectify it to God [...]. The falls and punishments of some are namely the warning and cure for others. Heaven is not angry although lucipher sinned in it, he shocked so many others all the same. St Magdalene is not ashamed in Heaven that until today they call her a sinner on Earth).

The lack of other musical sources, apart from hymnbooks, from the time before the establishment of the ensemble allows us thus to assume that in the 17th century and in the first half of the 18th century it was specifically the living tradition of hymn singing that dominated the musical life of the abbey.

Let us return now to the description of the ensemble’s activity. The tables below include the basic categories of expenditures connected with the musical life and the most interesting accounting entries that could be found in the preserved archival material.

Table 2: Expenses for organist and ‘kalikant’

year	organist	‘kalikant’	year	organist	‘kalikant’
1712	60	1	1785	116	9
1713	190	3	1786	87	7
1714	80	1	1788	86	5
1715	80	3	1789	128	5
1716	70	1	1790	118	25
1717	76	1	1791	111	5
1718	20	3	1792	148	1
1719	90	3	1793	148	1
1720	52	3	1794	80	3
1748	105	11	1795	151	4
1749	104	10	1796	154	3
1750	104	3	1797	169	1
1755	109	6	1798	191	1
1761	81	5	1799	37	7
1762	104	7	1800	7	1
1778	31	2	1801	13	1
1780	114	8	1802	9	1
1781	109	33	1803	4	1
1782	83	93	1804	4	1
1783	106	62	1805	4	1
1784	109	4			

⁵⁵ PL-STAb, *Reformationes generales...*, inv. 233, top. 53.

The table includes amounts paid to the organist and the “kalikant”.⁵⁶ We have already mentioned that the average income of the organist was ca. 80 zł per annum, whilst at least since mid 18th century the average annual pay went up to about 104 zł. The organist’s remuneration visibly surged in 1788, i.e. at the time when for the first time in the account ledgers the name Cichaski appeared.⁵⁷ From that moment the organist and the cantor receive 37.15 zł per quarter which makes an average annual salary of 150 zł. It is worth noting that the last time the quarterly payment for the organist was entered was in 1799. The later entries clearly refer to additional revenues, paid directly for the services rendered (first of all, the playing of the instrument, but also small jobs performed in the convent). The absence of ‘per diems’ for the musicians most probably means that at that time a separate book was kept for quarterly expenditures, covering most probably also other servers. A certain noticeable irregularity in the amount of the organist’s income arises from the postponement of the payment dates, which in fact did not happen that often. As in the case of the majority of monastic and parochial ensembles the “kalikant” was employed as the need arose, although in that period it was probably one person. In Staniątki, the payments for the “kalikant” were counted usually together with payments for the sacristian (in 1783–1786 it was a certain Gromadzki vel Gromacki). Interestingly, in 1781–1783 the “kalikant” received a remuneration for the whole year (“Kalikantemu za koscielną usługę Rocznią” – To Kalikant for the Annual church service); in 1781 it was 24 zł, and in 1782 and 1783 already 52 zł. Apart from this, he performed — similarly to other members of the ensemble — small jobs for which he received a separate remuneration (e.g. in 1782 a payment was made “Kalikantemu Zasług y od malowania ruznego” (To Kalikant for services and various painting jobs – 37 zł). It seems that in the second half of the 18th century a kalikant was employed on a permanent basis. The absence of a bigger number of entries that would unequivocally evidence this fact may arise from the inclusion of this cost into other, collective categories of expenditures classified separately.

One of the most interesting entries that may be found in the registers of expenditures of the convent in Staniątki are those that evidence the purchase of instruments. Unfortunately, we are not in possession of many entries of this type. We can learn from the chronicles that in 1721 a new organ was built. The account ledgers say that they most probably underwent an overhaul in 1761 — on August 16 the convent paid 54 zł “Organmistrzowi od Wychandozenia y sporządzenia Organ” (To the Organ-expert for the repairs and preparation of the organ) and 12 zł “Organiscie od Bozego Ciała co Organ prubował” (To the Organist from Corpus Christi who tested the Organ). The organ-expert was brought from Cracow which is evidenced by the next entry: “Forysiowi na drogę co odwoził rzemiesnikow do Krakowa” (To ‘Foryś’ for the road who took craftsmen to Cracow). The entry about ‘the repairs’ of the organ does not unfortunately allow to unequivocally assess whether the main instrument in the church is meant, although it seems very likely. The overhaul of this instrument may be perceived as an element of broader activity

⁵⁶ The amounts are approximate because quite often payments for various persons were entered in total. On the basis of the analysis of the earlier entries it may be presumed that this division was not always proportional – e.g. the “kalikant” obviously received a lower remuneration than the organist.

⁵⁷ In the catalogue of Tadeusz Maciejewski, Cichaski appears only beneath the date 1794, although Maciejewski assumed the years 1792–1825 as an approximate period of Cichaski’s activity. Cf. [Maciejewski, 1984, 21–22].

connected with musical life. It is known that on April 5, 1762 the convent bought two horns and two trumpets (“Za Walterny dwie y Trąby dwie” – For two French horns and two trumpets) for the amount of 126 zł oraz a mouthpiece for 7 zł (“Za Musztuk” – For the Mouthpiece.). The remaining two trumpets mentioned in the inventory of 1766 were bought earlier which would confirm the earlier hypothesis about the original composition of the ensemble in the beginnings of its activity. The next purchases of instruments appear only in the beginnings of the 19th century. In 1800 on February 8 the convent bought 2 clarinets (“Za parę Klarynetow” – For a pair of Clarinets) for the amount of 103 zł. Two years later, beneath the date of August 17, 1802 there is an entry about a purchase of a violin for 72 zł and a clavichord for the same amount. The purchase of the latter is particularly interesting. A clavichord was used mainly for practising, given its limited musical applications. Its purchase — next to other instruments — proves the growing needs of the ensemble. Another proof of this is also the extending of the collection of scores — e.g. in February 1800 the convent paid 100 zł for “Za Msze S: Figuralne Papiery dla Kantora kupione” (For Holy Masses: Figural papers bought for the cantor), whereas in December 1802 4 zł for “Kantorowi za Requiarnie papiery” (Requary papers for the cantor). Particularly intensive instrument purchases were made in 1803. In April the convent bought a violin for 72 zł, while 38 zł were spent “Na rozne Instrumenta dla Kapelli” (Various instruments for the Ensemble). Thereafter, in June the convent still bought a viola (for 36 zł) and a french horn (for 72 zł). That same year, the convent spent also 40 zł on “2. Msze Choralne” (2 choral masses) and the next 40 on “Papiery na 3. Msze y od przepisowania Ich” (Papers for 3 masses and for the copying of them). Also, in 1803, the abbey appropriated the amount of 36 zł for “Od Uczenia Spiwaczki” (Teaching of the Singer). In the following year, the convent paid 40 zł for the repairs of the violin. The latter probably referred to older instruments which were already in the ensemble’s stock.

In the beginning of the 19th century the composition of the ensemble was extended; according to the accounting records it was as follows:

Table 3: Number of musicians in the ensemble

1800	1801	1802	1803	1804	1805
8	7	9/8	8	9/8	9/10

In the records from the preceeding years (until 1799), the quantitative composition of the ensemble was not expressly stated, whereas the combining of the individual categories of expenditures does not make fact finding any easier. The names listed are the names of two trumpet-players (Jaskulski and Harzowski), and, apart from that, the records include the names of Cichaski and Podgurski (and a certain Gosiorowski in 1793). In 1791, the convent paid “Kapelistom 4 po zł: 2 Jaskulskiemu zł 3 kalikantemu 3” (To 4 ensemble members: 2 zł, to Jaskulski – 3 zł, to ‘kalikant’ – 3 zł” (in total 14 zł), which means that the ensemble at the time was composed of five persons, excluding the cantor and the organist. The extension of the size of the ensemble, the purchases of instruments and the ever more frequent expenditures on the purchase of music scores prove that in 1800–1805 the ensemble underwent a reorganisation which demonstrates its

growing professionalisation and which enabled the performing of an ever broader repertoire. This took place under the reign of prioress Apolonia Smidowiczówna who was elected to the office in 1799 (d. 1806). Smidowiczówna, who was earlier a housekeeper, knew how to take care of the convent's economic matters. Putting the finances to order increased the possibilities of the abbey in regard to ensuring a professional music setting, while the total annual expenditures for that purpose when compared to the last quarter of the 18th century have not increased much. Alas, accounting records from the following years are missing which prevents a more detailed recreation of the history of the ensemble at that time. This is a particularly severely felt gap because there is ample evidence that the first quarter of the 19th century was a peak period for the ensemble, as implicitly evidenced by musical sources (as mentioned in the next chapter of the book). The prioress at that time was Katarzyna Bogumiła Mechtylda Duwall, regarded as one of the most outstanding figures in the history of the convent.⁵⁸ She took the reign in 1808, after a two-year vacancy at this post caused by the tardiness of the partitioning powers who deliberately impeded the election of a prioress. Duwall not only took care of providing for the ensemble but she also carried into effect the overhaul of the church organ. As we can read in the second volume of the convent chronicle:⁵⁹

“Roku 1819 przerobiono cały organ z posiatem od dnia 10. maja a we wrześniu ukończono. Do naprawy organu, należała też cała galerya chóru. Zajmował się tą pracą organmistrz ze Lwowa, Jakób Krankowski. Zgodzony był za 85. dukatów a wszelkie materyały 100 fl. we walucie” (A.D. 1819 the whole organ was redone starting from May 10 until September. The repairs of the organ included also the renovation of the choir. This work was done by the organ-expert from Lvov, Jakób Krankowski. He was hired for 85 ducats, and all materials cost 100 florins in currency). Also from the time of prioress Duwall's reign comes an interesting testimony of musical life — a composition dedicated to her and performed on the occasion of her Name's Day on December 28, 1833 “Śpiew na błogi dzień imienia Jaśnie Wielmożnej i Najprzewielebniejszej Bogumiły Mechtyldy de Duwall Xieni Pani Zgromadzenia Staniąteckiego Z.R.S.O. Benedykta w hołdzie od kapeli i klasztoru [...] ofiarowany”.

After the death of prioress Duwall in 1842,⁶⁰ after a one-year's interregnum the rule over the community was taken over by Urszula Mechtylda Czajkowska. Her rule as the prioress coincided with a very difficult time, the deepening repressions of the partitioning government had a negative impact on the convent's finances. Staniątki were also not spared the tragic events of the Galician slaughter of 1846 — for five days since February 24, 1846 the convent was in danger, the flats of officials were robbed and some officials were beaten up. The convent's gate was chopped with axes and some of the intruders stormed inside and ran all over the convent

⁵⁸ [Krasnowolski, 1999, 207–212].

⁵⁹ *Kronika klasztoru staniąteckiego za czasów P.X.Z.L. Baryszewskiej. Na imieniny zebrana z dawnych kronik klasztornych* (The Chronicle of the Staniątki Convent from the Times of P.X.Z.L. Baryszewska. Collected from Old Convent chronicles to mark Her Name's Day.) vol. II, inv. 208, top. 721.

⁶⁰ Maciejewski gives an erroneous date of Duwall's death – 1844, cf. [Maciejewski, 1984, 22].

robbing it. In the convent chronicle we can find a copy of the letter of prioress Czajkowska to the Empress Caroline, in which she recalls the events:

“Smutne okoliczności zaszły w kraju naszym w roku przeszłym 1846 nie ominęły klasztoru naszego i majątku naszego, pomimo iż rozruchany lud zabijał, kaleczył oficyalistów i księży naszych niewinnych w niczem, zabrawszy tych nieszczęśników do urzędu cyrkularnego z dziedzińca klasztorowego i ze wszystkich folwarków. Poniszczyli wszystko w budynkach rąbiąc, tłukąc co tylko było naszego i biednych oficyalistów naszych. Nie zostawili ani okien, ani drzwi, ani pieców w całości. Spichlerze ze zborza [sic!] zrabowali, konie mordowali, wszystkie sprzęty gospodarskie zabrali, lasy okropnie zniszczyli” (The sad circumstances that happened in our country the past year in 1846 did not spare our convent and our property, despite the fact the unruly folk killed, injured our innocent officials and priests, taking these unfortunates to a circular office from the convent courtyard and from all the farms. They destroyed everything in the buildings by chopping, breaking everything that was ours and beating up our poor officials. They left neither doors nor windows nor stoves in one piece. They robbed the granaries of grain, murdered horses, took all farm tools, destroyed the forests terribly).⁶¹

There is no doubt that the events of 1846, which contributed to the deterioration of the material situation of the convent were one of the impulses for the disbanding of the permanent musical ensemble. The ensemble was eventually disbanded by the decision of prioress Czajkowska in 1849 — nb. the information about it can be found in the part of the convent chronicle which speaks about the establishment of a mission in the Staniątki property after the events of 1846.

“Cała nadwiślańska okolica, a szczególnie od Niepołomic, tłumnie śpieszyła do Staniątek, na słuchanie nauk i oczyszczenie sumienia swego. Codziennie dwie Msze święte śpiewane były. Jedna rano, Wotywa przy towarzyszeniu organ; druga, Suma przy towarzyszeniu całej orkiestry, którą klasztor utrzymywał aż do roku 1849” (The entire Vistulan neighbourhood, particularly from side of Niepołomice, hurried in crowds to Staniątki, to listen to lectures and clear its conscience. Every day two Holy Masses were sung. One in the morning: Votives with the accompaniment of the organ; and the second one: the High Mass with the participation of the whole orchestra that the convent kept as long as until 1849).⁶²

It is highly likely that the services with the participation of the ensemble, mentioned by the chronicler, were one of the last instances of its activity. The disbanding of the ensemble,

⁶¹ *Kronika klasztoru staniąteckiego za czasów P.X.Z.L. Baryszewskiej. Na imieniny zebrana z dawnych kronik klasztornych* (The Chronicle of the Staniątki Convent from the Times of P.X.Z.L. Baryszewska. Collected from Old Convent chronicles to mark Her Name's Day), vol. II, inv. 208, top. 721.

⁶² *Kronika klasztoru staniąteckiego za czasów P.X.Z.L. Baryszewskiej. Na imieniny zebrana z dawnych kronik klasztornych* (The Chronicle of the Staniątki Convent from the Times of P.X.Z.L. Baryszewska. Collected from Old Convent chronicles to mark Her Name's Day), vol. II, inv. 208, top. 721.

just like its establishment were more likely a process which ended in its formal disbanding. Unfortunately, no documents have been preserved that would provide a proof of the moment of the disbanding. However, the date given in the chronicle may be regarded as reliable. Sister Kaładulska wrote down the convent history not much later. It seems that the disbanding of the ensemble was tantamount to complete resignation from including vocal-instrumental music (this does not include the organ, of course) in the services. This is evidenced by an inventory made in 1858 which enumerates the instruments preserved after the ensemble. It is underlined in the inventory that all instruments are very worn.⁶³

Coming towards the end of the deliberations on the musical ensemble, let us try to point out the names of the members of the ensemble and other secular musicians. Below you will find the lists of organists and cantors from the second half of the 19th century. Below the names are listed of musicians known to us, with the dates in parentheses. Anonymous boy-singers were omitted — in their case it is impossible to determine their identity, or even to unequivocally state that in the subsequent years we deal with the same person. The earliest named secular musician was Kazimierz Boczkowski, who stayed in Staniątki in 1700–1709. Information about the remaining musicians has been found in the convent chronicles and account ledgers.

1. Kazimierz Boczkowski (1700–1709)
2. Jakub Surnikowski [organist] (1721)
3. Marcin Surnikowski [cantor] (1721)
4. Józef Cichaski (named in the account ledgers in 1788–1790, 1793–1799; was active in the convent from 1788 until 1827)
5. Jaskulski (1788–1796)
6. Harzowski [Hazoski, Harzoski] (1780, 1784, 1788–1798)
7. Paweł Dynowski (1803–1805)
8. Marcin Pochwalski (1789, 1792, 1796, zm. 1801)
9. Kasper Pochwalski (1801, 1802)
10. Dudkiewicz (1801–1802)
11. Ostrowski (1803–1805)
12. Sadowski (1805)
13. NN female singer (1800–1802, 1805)

⁶³ *Inwentar des Vermögens der Benediktiner Nonnen Conventus zu Staniątki [...]*, inv. 653, top. A 164.

Unfortunately, despite the abundance of sources that have been analysed during the research on the Staniątki archives, other names of the Staniątki musicians could not be found. This arises from the fact that music played a functional role whereas musicians themselves were treated like the remaining convent servants that were not individually named in the chronicles.

It is very characteristic that among the names known to us some repeat themselves, as in the case of Pochwalski (father and son), Surnikowski, and, later on, Leszczyński. This proves a quite a frequent practice, encountered also in other ensembles, of recruiting the ensemble members among the relatives. Particularly interesting is also the coincidence of first names and surnames of Marcin and Kasper Pochwalski. It is known that a painter worked in Staniątki, by the name of Marcin Pochwalski (living, according to the *Polish Biographical Dictionary*, in the years 1740?–1800). What is more, Marcin Pochwalski had a son, Kasper Apolinary (January 8, 1783 – April 17, 1831), also a painter, whose son was Józef Kasper (March 5, 1816, Brzezcie – July 2, 1875, Cracow). Provided this coincidence is not accidental, we would deal here with a rare case when a father and a son worked in one centre, playing at the same time the role of a painter and a member of the ensemble. A certain analogy could be provided by the case of Izydor Leszczyński, a painter from the Cracow guild who upon the death of his wife, together with his son, joined the monastery of the Pauline Fathers on Jasna Góra. Władysław Leszczyński (1717–1780) was one of the most outstanding musicians active in this centre in the 17th century. It is not known, however, whether, like his father, he also earned his living as a painter.

3 Music in Staniątki after the Disbanding of the Ensemble

In the second half of the 19th century the economic situation of the convent left much to be desired not only due to external factors, but also as a result of an unfortunate selection of property managers (which the nuns not always had had an impact on). Despite this, the position of an organist still existed and even the construction of a new organ was started. Thus, an important testimony of the musical life in the convent are documents related to the purchase of a new organ.⁶⁴ By the decision of Zofia Baryszewska, in 1881 a contract for the construction of a new organ was signed. The contractor was Jan Grocholski, a well-known organ-expert from Stary Sącz. Unfortunately, the selection of the organ-expert was totally ill-advised. Already two years after the construction was completed, the instrument was in fact unfit for playing which was caused by a faulty structure, although Grocholski tried to explain the problems with the excessive humidity in the church. In 1884 he was called to Staniątki in order to make the indispensable repairs and to varnish the pipes.

In 1892 another organ-expert arrived in Staniątki, Jan Fall, an organ-expert from Strzyrzyce who — according to the records in the chronicle — thoroughly rebuilt the organ. During rebuilding it turned out that the organ was tilted towards the church which confirms the unreliable performance of his task by Grocholski. It seems that Fall's works brought some effect because in the following years he was only called to tune the instrument (1895 and 1897). Grocholski's instrument survived until 1913 when a new organ was ordered at the famous Rieger brothers'

⁶⁴ PL-STAb, unnumbered loose records and gatherings, call no. 651 top. A 165.

company in Karniów. Kazmierz Żebrowski, an organ-expert from Lvov, representing the Rieger Brothers acted as an intermediary between the company and the abbey. In 1924, the organ was ‘reconstructed’ (the repair probably involved the change of a part of the pipes) by Stanisław Żebrowski from Cracow. At first the cooperation of the convent with Żebrowski was awful — in a letter of March 11, 1924 he gives the nuns an ultimatum, expecting them to send 500 zł within three days. It is not known how the nuns reacted to Żebrowski’s letter, however, an agreement must have been reached since already in May he signed the receipt of 100 milion zł⁶⁵ for the agreed reconstruction.

Despite the disbanding of the ensemble in 1849, the monastery still kept the cantor, alongside the organist. This function was kept in the convent until 1880. In the third volume of the *Kronika* we can find the names of cantors and organists active in Staniątki in the second half of the 19th century. We read in it:

“For a long time there was a custom that novices and pupils learnt to sing with the cantor whom our convent maintained. Only those can be named here whose names our memory recalls. 1. [Józef] Wygrzywalski, a famous musician, left in 1847. 2. Józef Kunstman left in 1848. 3. Walenty Czajkowski left before 1853. 4. Ignacy Bobrzyński worked until 1871. 5. Franci: Frälich left in 1863. 6. Wincenty Leszczyński worked until 1868. 7. Leszczyński, his brother, worked until 1878. 8. Stysiński worked until 1880. Organists provided singing as the need arose. And, finally, prioress Łazowska ordered Sister Willibalda Kmietowicz to sing herself in accordance with the Gregoryan Laws in which she was trained: which was agreed in 1888.

Organists in Staniątki.

1. Mr Parys, an emigrant. 2. Józef Cichawski, a cantor and organist. 3. Teodor Podgórski, a famous organist, a man of high morals, did not like interfere with anything, was thorough, was never late and never failed to do what he committed himself to. Died in Staniątki in 1879. 4. His successor was Waszak. 5. Machlarzewski. 6. Jan Kowalski assumed the post on June 24, 1883. 7. Józef Fijałek assumed the post on December 1, 1891”.⁶⁶

Since 1888 the teaching of singing, by the decision of prioress Wanda Genowefa Abundancja Łada-Łazowska was assigned to Sister Wilibalda Kmietowicz. This moment is an important turning point in the history of the musical life of the Staniątki convent — it saw an increased interest in choral singing and attempts to revive the Gregorian tradition. This change was not only the outcome of an increased interest in the history of its own convent, but was also an effect of a longer process that began with the disbanding of a permanent musical ensemble. The gap that developed as a result of resigning from a more elaborate musical setting of the liturgy had to be filled somehow. At that time, the hymnbook repertoire probably no longer provided a real alternative to the choral; let us remember that the latest of the Staniątki hymnbooks (St P)

⁶⁵ The year 1924 is a period of hyperinflation the end to which was put by Grabski’s monetary reform.

⁶⁶ *Kronika...* (Chronicle...) vol. III, p. 162.

comes from 1837 and contains only the lyrics. By the way, the return to the choral perfectly matched the tendencies that ruled in the Universal Church then. It was specifically during the pontificate of Leon XIII (1878–1903) that the work continued on the renewal of the liturgy in the spirit of the choral tradition. Not much earlier, in 1875 Solesmes Prosper Guéranger died, who was one of the initiators of the movement of the liturgical renewal. In 1887 Staniątki played host to a Polish trapist from the French convent in Macon, Sister Cecylia Mińska. Her photograph can be found in the convent *Chronicle*.

Figure 13: Prioress Wanda Łazowska (left), S. Cecylia Mińska, *Kronika...*, vol. III

Mińska stayed in Staniątki several months at the order of Cardinal Dunajewski. Admittedly, she could not fully find herself in the community life of the Staniątki nuns.⁶⁷ Nonetheless, prioress Kmietowicz, using her presence, decided to revive choral singing.

“Upon having learnt from Sister Cecylia that at the Trapist Nuns’ there is pure Gregorian singing in the choir, which at that time the whole world over was becoming ever more popular, the prioress decided to introduce a change which was quite difficult to introduce because older nuns, while educated in the previous kind of singing, almost had to learn everything anew”.⁶⁸

⁶⁷ The chronicle mentions with a bit of sneer that Mińska, wanting to show the austerity of her life, in winter when her cell was heated, used to open the window as a result of which she caught a cold and only caused further problems.

⁶⁸ *Kronika...*, vol. III, p. 125.

The reform of singing that took place in 1887–1888 is also a turning point in the present work because from that moment on the nuns took again a full responsibility for the musical life of the abbey, while it was practically reduced to only one of the many earlier existing dimensions. This turn of events should not be assessed negatively because we need to remember it was the effect of very many factors (including economic factors) that the nuns had only a partial impact on. The unusual vitality of the choral singing and the nuns' musicality manifests itself in the fact that in that period they returned to their own, older musical sources, as mentioned in the previous chapter. The Staniątki nuns take a huge credit for their unusual care for the musical heritage — the music collection no longer in use was not (as it happened in many cases) utilized or simply destroyed. Quite to the contrary, it found a safe refuge in the convent library, together with the hymnbooks.

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